

Mapping a Network: Analyzing Human-AI Relationship in Ishiguro's Sciences Fictions through a Posthumanist Lens

Xiaoyue Wang

1. Introduction to the research question

Although Kazuo Ishiguro is not typically classified as a traditional science fiction writer, his eight published novels include *Never Let Me Go* (2005) and *Klara and the Sun* (2021), both of which incorporate rich science fiction elements and have achieved great literary success. *Never Let Me Go* (hereinafter referred to as “*Never*”) was shortlisted for the 2005 Man Booker Prize, while *Klara and the Sun* (hereinafter referred to as “*Klara*”) was his first novel published after receiving the Nobel Prize in Literature in 2017, and it was longlisted for the 2021 Booker Prize. These two novels feature artificial intelligence clones and robots as the main characters and narrators separately, focusing on ethical issues arising from technological advancements and the existential value of human.

Posthumanism originates from Foucault's (1966) concept of “the death of man” in *The Order of Things*, which challenges the central role of humans in the production of knowledge and inspires a reconsideration of the relationships between humans and non-human entities. Wolfe (2010, p.15) argued that “posthumanism names a historical moment in which the decentering of the human by its imbrication in technical, medical, informatic, and economic networks is increasingly impossible to ignore”, stressing its ethical focus. In Ishiguro's fictions, he brings out “a posthuman perception that challenges the conventional notions of AI as a machine devoid of emotions”(Ajeesh & Rukmini, 2023), though they are subordinate beings created to serve humans according to these novels' context, which typifies the relationship between human and AI (clones in “*Never*”) ¹ in these two novel, reflecting

¹ Although clones and robots belong to different categories from the perspective of natural sciences, Ishiguro's science fiction novels do not aim to depict future technology. Instead, they focus on presenting the emotions of clones and robots (referred to as artificial friends in “*Klara*”) from a humanistic and ethical perspective. Therefore, I will use the term artificial intelligence (AI) to refer to both.

posthumanist elements. “*Never*” is over 96,000 words long, while “*Klara*” is over 89,000 words. Despite their similar lengths, what kind of relationships between clones or robots and humans are explored in the two novels. Also, due to the extensive psychological depictions and dialogues in these two novels, as well as the complexity and contradictions of character relationships, including AI-AI, human-human, and AI-human interactions, analyzing these relationships through traditional close reading becomes challenging. Network analysis can serve as a potential approach that uses quantitative methods to address this problem.

The expected research goal is to present the relationships between artificial intelligence and humans in these two novels through network analysis. How do these two novels respectively portray the relationships between AI and AI, humans and humans, and AI and humans, and what do these novels explore by presenting such character relationship?

2. Data

2.1 Data collection

Since TXT versions of “*Never*” and “*Klara*” are not available, I used Python’s pdfplumber library to extract text from the PDF versions of these two books and convert it into TXT format. Then I got TXT files of these two novels, with 96,532 (*Never_raw.txt*) and 90,200 (“*Klara_raw.txt*”) words separately in English.

2.2 Data cleanup

After the process of extraction and convert, there are some extra information, such as publication information and table of content are included in these two files. A manual review was performed to remove these unwanted content, keeping only the body of the novels. After deleting the extra information, the “*Never.txt*” file had 96,465 words, and the “*Klara.txt*” file had 89,781 words.

Based on the *Characters List By Chapter* provided by Book Companion (refer to *Klara and the Sun Characters Listed With Descriptions.pdf* and *Never Let Me Go characters Listed With Descriptions.pdf*), character names were manually cross-referenced and standardized. Different references to the same character were unified, such as “Madame” and “Marie-Claude,” as well as “Kath” and “Kathy,” both referring to the same person.

However, in *Klara*, things became more complicate. Because both Josie’s mother, Chrissie, and Rick’s mother, Helen, are mentioned in the novel, it has led to issues with referring to kinship relationships. To prevent such issues from affecting name frequency statistics, the names of the three characters—Josie’s mother, Chrissie; Josie’s father, Paul; and Rick’s mother, Helen, were manually validated and replaced in the text. For example, mentions of “mother” (mom/mum) in paragraphs where Josie refers to her mother were standardized to “Chrissie.” The edited documents are named *Never_Label_Name.txt* and *Klara_Label_Name.txt*.

3. Analysis

3.1 Character name frequency statistics

First, according to the *Characters List By Chapter*, the character name dictionaries was created separately. Next, in the document with standardized character aliases, I found the frequency of each characters’ names by creating Python function to read the file and search for names. The character names and their corresponding frequencies were stored in descending order in the files *Klara_Name_Frequencies_Sorted.csv* and *Never_Name_Frequencies_Sorted.csv*. And then, histograms of distribution of character names (Figure 1) in these two novels was created by matplotlib library.

the Manager, who interacts with Klara both at the beginning and the end of the novel, but their names are not mentioned throughout.

An interesting point is that though the clone Kathy and the robot Klara serve as narrators in their respective stories, their name frequencies are relatively low among these primary characters. In *Never*, Kathy’s name appears far less frequently compared to the other two clones, Tommy and Ruth, accounting for roughly one-eighth of their combined mentions. Similarly, in *Klara*, the frequencies of human characters such as Josie, Rick, and Chrissie are significantly higher than Klara’s. It reflects the main theme of the novel, where the human world is observed and understood through the robot’s perspective. As Ajeesh & Rukmini (2023) pointed out, Klara “develops an almost clairvoyant understanding of people’s behaviour.”

For both novels, the data processing workflows and code were nearly the same, except for the manual validation steps specific to each text. To reduce the length of a single workflow file and avoid excessive data causing visual clutter and slowdowns, the analysis was conducted using two separate files for better readability.

To analyze the distribution pattern of character name frequencies, a power-law distribution test was performed. The frequency rank of characters was set as the x-axis, and the frequency as the y-axis. A double-logarithmic scale was used to fit a linear regression line, and the result was evaluated based on the sum of squared errors.

Figure2 Log-Log Plot of Character Rank with Turning point in *Never* and *Klara*

As shown in Figure 2, the distribution of character name frequencies in *Never* conforms to a power-law distribution, with a fitted line slope of -1.8349, exhibiting a long-tail effect. The top three characters in frequency distribution are the clones Tommy, Ruth, and Kathy, with Tommy and Ruth far exceeding Kathy, the narrator. The following are secondary characters associated with Hailsham (the school where the clones reside), including humans such as Marie-Claude, Lucy, and Emily, as well as the clone Chrissie. A notable rank threshold appears at 8, with a frequency of 80, marking the division between primary and secondary characters. Among the primary characters, Tommy and Ruth play a more important role in the story's narratives, compared to Kathy.

To construct the character relationship diagram, it is necessary to reduce noise from low-frequency characters in the long-tail section while retaining as much information as possible, ensuring a suitable data size for sufficient information. Therefore, a secondary turning point with the frequency of 5 was chosen, and names with frequencies below 5 were removed.

Similarly, the character name frequency distribution in *Klara* also aligns with a power-law distribution, with a fitted line slope of -2.2115. A significant threshold appears at rank 11, with a frequency of 74. To retain as much information as possible in the relationship diagram, names with frequencies below 5 were removed.

By analyzing the frequency of character names (both the frequency distribution and characteristics), we can get a basic understanding of the importance of characters in the novel and the distribution of primary and secondary characters. However, to explore more about the patterns of character relationships, the character co-occurrence matrix will be created.

3.2 Character co-occurrence network map

Moretti (2011) defined character connections based on dialogues in his analysis of *Hamlet*, as dialogue is the most fundamental interaction mode for characters in dramatic texts. However, fictional narratives require different methods for character network extraction because of their unique characteristics (Labatut, V., & Bost, X., 2019).

Since these two novels' paragraphs vary greatly in length, and many dialogues consist of single-sentence paragraphs, there is often a lack of sufficient context to capture character interactions. To address this, an automated analysis with Python sliding windows (window size is set to 50, meaning each window covering 50 words) was employed to analyze character co-occurrence relationships. After constructing the character co-occurrence matrix, different colors were used to label character types (e.g., humans and clones in *Never*, and humans and robots in *Klara*). The resulting co-occurrence network diagrams are shown below:

Character Co-occurrence Network in *Never* (Clones in Blue, Humans in Red)

Character Co-occurrence Network in *Klara* (Robots in Blue, Humans in Red)

Figure 3 Character co-occurrence network in *Never* and *Klara*

Never focuses on the emotional world of clones, centering the novel on the interactions between clones. In the story, clones are subordinate beings created for human organ replacement, and their lives serve humans. The narrative illustrates the

conflicting emotions between clones and humans. On the one hand, in Hailsham (the school for clones in the novel), humans educate and house the clones, recognizing that clones also have human-like emotions and souls. On the other hand, humans view clones as tools, and they think that the clones cannot change their fate of sacrificing themselves for humans.

In *Never*, the “central relationship triangle” among the three cloned friends, Tommy, Ruth and Kathy, is a key element of the novel. It reflects friendship and love, as well as jealousy and control, presenting the humanity of the clones. The relationship network in *Never* demonstrates the coexistence and mutual influence between humans and clones, while *Klara* focuses on the depiction of human emotions from the perspective of a robot. Besides Klara, other robots like Rosa, Rex and Sung Yi are on the outskirts of the relationship network, appearing with other characters less frequently, and they have less interaction with humans.

Through the above steps, combining with the text, we can find the basic relationship patterns, such as the friendships and romantic relationships of Tommy and Ruth, as well as the vastly different social backgrounds and mutual attraction between friends Josie and Rick. Both these two-way relationships occupy important portions of the narratives, reflecting the complexity of human nature. Unlike the “central relationship triangle” among the three cloned friends in *Never*, the core of *Klara* is Josie. Around Josie, three kind of main complex emotions are developed, Rick’s youthful friendship and affection for Josie, Klara’s unconditional friendship and dedication to Josie, and Josie’s mother Chrissie’s love and implicit control over her. In the context of *Klara*, to maintain superior genes, Chrissie genetically edited both of her children. As a result of side effects, Josie’s older sister Sal has already died, and Josie is also badly ill. And Chrissie is so afraid of losing her daughter that she even wants Klara to imitate and replace Josie. As the narrator, Klara meticulously observes and experiences complex human behaviors and emotions from her perspective as a robot. She offers her unconditional friendship to Josie and tries to restore Josie’s health

through her own methods, such as praying to the sun.

3.3 Character centrality measures

In order to further understand the roles and influences of characters within the relationship network, I used Python to calculate character centrality measures, as shown in Figure 3-a and Figure 3-b. In *Never*, the narrative centers around Tommy and Ruth, whose degree centrality and closeness centrality are the highest.

	Degree Centrality	Betweenness Centrality	Closeness Centrality	Eigenvector Centrality
Tommy	0.807692308	0.193846154	0.838709677	0.597222656
Ruth	0.730769231	0.223076923	0.787878788	0.614728468
Lucy	0.384615385	0.318461538	0.619047619	0.08199483
Chrissie	0.192307692	0	0.52	0.279254408
Emily	0.461538462	0.107692308	0.65	0.082088215
Rodney	0.192307692	0	0.52	0.257600793
Kathy	0.538461538	0.42	0.684210526	0.2750562
Laura	0.384615385	0.189230769	0.619047619	0.069320184
Geraldine	0.269230769	0.233846154	0.565217391	0.06399206
Keffers	0.192307692	0.226153846	0.530612245	0.009715766
Judy	0.230769231	0.215384615	0.541666667	0.04079992
Hannah	0.192307692	0	0.530612245	0.030796801
Roger	0.192307692	0.178461538	0.52	0.009353584
Morningdal	0.153846154	0.110769231	0.5	0.005569389
George	0.230769231	0	0.553191489	0.013620202
Roy	0.230769231	0.156923077	0.541666667	0.015276009
Lenny	0.115384615	0	0.509803922	0.019388041
Martin	0.153846154	0	0.509803922	0.032634564
Christopher	0.076923077	0	0.490566038	0.014574217
Marie-Clau	0.5	0.250769231	0.666666667	0.13175047
Patricia	0.076923077	0	0.481481481	0.006025418
Arthur	0.038461538	0	0.464285714	0.010888508
Moir	0.076923077	0	0.456140351	0.013123752
Midge	0.076923077	0	0.456140351	0.02206971
Marge	0.076923077	0	0.40625	0.002073325
Jack	0.038461538	0	0.4	8.69E-05
Steve	0.076923077	0	0.393939394	0.000421011

Figure 3-a Character centrality measures in *Never*

	Degree Centrality	Betweenness Centrality	Closeness Centrality	Eigenvector Centrality
Josie	1	0	1	0.597784409
Rick	0.904761905	0.119047619	0.913043478	0.465156295
Chrissie	0.761904762	0.085714286	0.807692308	0.435528716
Klara	0.904761905	0.076190476	0.913043478	0.298697498
Helen	0.428571429	0	0.636363636	0.226446738
Paul	0.523809524	0.119047619	0.677419355	0.171988588
Manager	0.714285714	0	0.777777778	0.071209665
Capaldi	0.523809524	0.138095238	0.677419355	0.15618634
Melania	0.523809524	0.133333333	0.677419355	0.146313267
Vance	0.523809524	0.352380952	0.677419355	0.095871638
Rosa	0.476190476	0.395238095	0.65625	0.024297541
McBain	0.285714286	0	0.583333333	0.048235233
Rex	0.238095238	0.033333333	0.567567568	0.007150661
Sal	0.428571429	0.038095238	0.636363636	0.038916443
Danny	0.333333333	0.019047619	0.6	0.031963869
Beggar Man	0.428571429	0.419047619	0.636363636	0.016767463
Missy	0.19047619	0	0.552631579	0.012085788
Coffee Cup	0.333333333	0	0.6	0.006239331
Ryan	0.19047619	0	0.552631579	0.018185884
Cindy	0.19047619	0.142857143	0.552631579	0.009031736
Raincoat M	0.333333333	0.185714286	0.6	0.004723612
Sung Yi	0.142857143	0	0.538461538	0.007124455

Figure 3-b Character centrality measures in *Klara*

In *Klara*, it's evident that Josie, with the highest degree centrality is the center of these characters' network. And Klara's betweenness centrality is relatively low, despite the fact that many characters interact with her, especially other robots Rosa,

and Emily, who taught them in the boarding school, which reveals the emotions that arise between humans and clones during their interactions. In *Klara*, though Josie occupies a central position in the character co-occurrence network, this actually originates from Klara's emphasis on her. However, does Josie reciprocate Klara's friendship to the same extent? Even if AI and humans share similar emotions, can AI receive equal respect from humans? Moreover, despite Klara's meticulous observations and sensitivity, can she truly replace humans? These questions, which relate to the deeper themes of the novel, require further close reading of the text and cannot be directly answered through the co-occurrence network.

However, it is interesting that computational methods revealed some facts I hadn't noticed during reading. For example, these two narrators is not mentioned frequently among the main characters and does not occupy a central position in the narrative. Also, the central roles in the narrative are mainly pairs of friends, such as Ruth and Tommy, and Josie and Rick. The narrators often act as bystanders, telling the stories of others, and this observer perspective is particularly notable in *Klara*, as many of the connections are based on her observations of other characters. By presenting such character relationships patterns, the two novels presents the elements of posthumanism by exploring the issues of instrumentality and subjectivity in clones and robots. The former stresses that clones, as sacrificial beings in the human world, possess their own emotions. The latter portrays human behavior and emotions in the world of robots, emphasizing the robot's sincerity and human-like qualities, though she also exists as a tool to serve humans.

4.2 Potential biases and limitation

In the data collection stage, since I didn't find reliable TXT versions of these two novels, converting the raw text from PDF to TXT format during the text data processing phase may lead to the loss of text structure and formatting details, such as paragraph breaks, despite manual checking was conducted.

For the character names extraction part, I planned to use Python to conduct Named Entity Recognition (NER) first. Based on a manual spot check comparing the `en_core_web_sm` and `en_core_web_lg` models from the SpaCy library, I found that the Transformer model has a higher accuracy in identifying complete names. However, there is a significant amount of noise in the data, such as place names like “Hailsham” and “Cottages” (both are locations in *Never*), which requires manual cleaning and document updates. To ensure accuracy, I finally chose to manually revise the character aliases and build a dictionary to prevent the occurrence of noise data. The results were compared and validated against the NER operation results of the `en_core_web_trf` model. However, both novels are written in the first person, which may affect the frequency of names and co-occurrence relationships, such as instances where the narrator cannot be identified. Although this research, which draws conclusions through computational methods primarily, the text covers over 186,000 words in total, the number of characters is relatively small (especially in *Klara*). In fact, I spent much time annotating the name data. From this research, I have realized the importance of data cleaning, especially in *Klara*, the novel often refers to characters by aliases. For example, Josie’s mother, Chrissie, is called “the Mother” at the most of the time, and also she is referred to “Mom” or “Mum” by Josie, which can be easily confused with Rick’s reference to his mother, Helen. Accurate name identification is important for creating a co-occurrence matrix. I manually annotated the character names and conducted a thorough reading check after the annotations were completed. However, the accuracy may still be affected by personal subjective biases.

When creating the character co-occurrence matrix, I firstly considered using paragraphs as the basis. However, due to the varying lengths of the paragraphs, the results were much less than expected, making it unfit for mapping character co-occurrence network. Some dialogues were presented as single paragraphs, lacking contextual information to determine the characters involved. So I decided to use a Python sliding window approach, and I tried the effect of different window sizes. As

Labatuti and Bost (2016, p.56) pointed out the importance of “assessing the relevance of using dynamic networks instead of static ones, and/or to identify which parameter values are optimal (e.g. size of the narrative unit when detecting co-occurrences, or of the sliding window when building dynamic networks)” in network analysis, it’s necessary to find a suitable way to check co-occurrences based on the text’s own features. Further attempts could be done to reduce the possible bias, such as segmenting the text based on dialogue “events” manually, grouping similar dialogues into a single segment. However, I did not conduct this manual annotation because of time limitation. This aspect might be improved upon in future work. For the wordcloud part, though I have tailored the stopwords, the information remains relatively complex and limited in clarity. Combining the method of wordcloud with topic modeling to categorize the text may help convey the information more effectively. In fact, every step of data processing can lead to the generation of “dirty data”, affecting the accuracy of the data. In digital humanities research, it is important to clean the data as thoroughly as possible and to be aware of potential biases at each stage.

References:

1. BookCompanion. (n.d.). *NEVER LET ME GO characters by list chapter*. Retrieved from https://www.bookcompanion.com/never_let_me_go_character_list.html
2. BookCompanion. (n.d.). *KLARA AND THE SUN characters by chapter*. Retrieved from https://www.bookcompanion.com/klara_and_the_sun_character_list.html
3. Ishiguro, K. (2021). *Klara and the Sun*. Alfred A. Knopf.
4. Ishiguro, K. (2010). *Never Let Me Go*. Vintage Books. (Originally published: 2005)
5. Foucault, M. (2002). *The order of things*. Routledge. (Originally published: 1966)
6. Wolfe, C. (2010). *What is posthumanism?*. U of Minnesota P.
7. Moretti, F. (2011). Network theory, plot analysis.
8. Labatut, V., & Bost, X. (2019). Extraction and analysis of fictional character networks: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 52, 89. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3344548>
9. Ajeesh, A. K., & Rukmini, S. (2023). Posthuman perception of artificial intelligence in science

fiction: An exploration of Kazuo Ishiguro's *Klara and the Sun*. *AI & Society*, 38, 853–860.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-022-01533-9>